

Characterization of Antimicrobial Compounds Producing pigmented Halophilic bacteria *Kocuria flava* from Dhanushkodi of Pamban Island

Sweta Tejaswi Thumma¹, Suvarnalatha Devi Potireddy*

¹*Sri Padmavati Mahila Visvavidyalayam, Department of Applied Microbiology, Tirupati -517502, Andhra Pradesh.*

**Corresponding author*

Abstract: *The finding of new Antimicrobial compound from marine source took a lot of interest in the present research, in which we aimed to screen an extreme halophiles from sea water for production of Antibiotics. We screened secondary metabolites producing bacteria from the water samples of Dhanushkodi of pamban island of Tamil nadu, we used spread plate technique on medium Zobell marine agar, and eight pigmented bacterial isolates were screened based on its color, morphology, antimicrobial activity and biochemical characterization. UV-visible spectroscopy analysis and Phylogenetic analysis were carried out to identify the Bacteria. Among eight isolates we found an extreme halophile showed maximum inhibitory effect against human pathogens and named it as MB4. It was concluded that based on the 16srRNA sequencing the isolate MB4 strain is *Kocuria flava* which has potential to produce new promising antibiotics.*

Keywords: *Bio-active compound, Antimicrobial activity, Secondary metabolites, UV-spectroscopy, pathogens.*

1. INTRODUCTION

A huge treasure of bioactive secondary metabolites was found stronger in Marine bacteria when compared to the terrestrial microorganisms [1]. Some studies indicated that compounds found in the marine plants and organisms were formed by the symbiotic marine microorganism associated with them [2]. Due to increase of Multi drug resistance bacteria to the available antibiotics there is need to search for new drug or new antibiotics which led to screen for new antimicrobial compounds of secondary metabolites. According to the research 70% of the earth is cover with the oceans and sea has been less explored for finding new potentially active bio-substance. Previous studies stated that marine bacteria can be applied to the combat epizootics in the aquatic ecosystem, Marine bacteria and fungi have the ability to produce antitumor, antibacterial, antifungal and antiviral substances [3]. A report by Janaki Devi (2013) showed that in marine microorganisms produced more than 50,000 natural bio active compounds were discovered so far among them 8,000 compounds have bactericidal activity [4]. So, there is a need to isolate new bacteria from the marine sources and its characterization of secondary metabolites is an important challenge. In our study we focused on the search for potent antimicrobial drugs from non-infective bacteria which over the resistance exhibited against the existing antibiotic is most important [5].

Multi drug resistance bacteria such as *Enterococcus* and *Staphylococcus* being a serious issue in clinical or hospital environment so there is a need to screen new drugs with broad spectrum [6]. About 40% of women and 12% of men suffers with Urinary tract infection (UTI) which is the most common infective disease with highest percentage of occurrence was found in women because of their biological condition, bacteria may invade due to sexual intercourse, pregnancy, and family history [7]. Marine bacteria are prosperous source which come through the new bioactive compounds, so far marine Actinomycetes are known as the efficient groups of natural metabolite producers as they produce naturally occurring antibiotics of bioactive compounds [8]. In drug discovery natural products played a major role. Exploitation of less explored ecosystem is necessary, Indian marine ecosystem is an

important source for microbial expedition hence the bio active compounds in the Indian bay of Bengal are need to be surveyed . Due to bacterial resistance to the drugs there is a need to discover new drugs. Previously for those searching unknown microbial strains is an effective approach to obtain new bioactive compound [9].Microbial metabolites are good source to find new therapeutic drugs [10].Marine microbes developed unique physiological and metabolic capabilities which ensure their survival in extreme habitats. Hence the production of metabolites would be different when compared to the terrestrial micro-organism [11].The primary role of antimicrobial activity can be antagonize competitors with an ability to sense the competing microbes by using an auto inducer which is a small hormone like molecule helps in the form of chemical communication involves in detecting and responding [12].In food science and technology chemical antimicrobial compounds were used widely as preservative to inhibit the growth of unwanted microbes and also to extend food's shelf life [13].

2. MATERIAL AND METHODS

2.1. Sample collection

The sample collection site is Dhanushkodi which is located at tip of an island named Pamban in south-east of Tamil nadu state. Marine water sample is collected at the depth of 10 meter sealed properly in a sterile container to avoid contamination and brought to laboratory. To keep the exact count of population qualitatively and quantitatively the sample was kept in refrigerator at 4°C to minimize the microbial metabolic activity.

2.2. Isolation of marine bacteria

The Marine water sample was serially diluted and placed on agar plate by spread plate method on Zobell marine agar media. The agar plates were placed in incubator for 5-7 days 37°C for incubation. After incubation the colonies developed were studied and sub cultured repeatedly to get pure culture on Zobell marine agar media [14]. All these bacterial colonies were chosen based on its color, elevation, opacity, surface appearance and margin for further characterization.

2.3. Collection of Test organisms

UTI causing pathogens such as *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Escherichia coli*, *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, *Proteus mirabilis*, along with few other clinical pathogenic bacteria such as *Salmonella paratyphi b*, *Actinobacteria* and Fungi *Aspergillus niger*, *Aspergillus flavus*, *Fusarium fujikuroi*, *Aspergillus Clavatus* were collected from department of Microbiology, Sri Venkateswara Institute of Medical Sciences, Tirupati of Andhra Pradesh. The clinical pathogens were stored at 4°C until used.

2.4. Screening of Marine Isolates for its Antimicrobial Activity

Clinical pathogens were incubated in nutrient broth for 24hrs at 37°C. These cultures were swabbed on Mueller Hinton agar media plates using sterile cotton swab uniformly. Around 3mm depth wells were made respectively on to the culture swabbed plates. Aseptically 10µl of overnight marine bacterial culture were inoculated in the well and plates were incubated for 24hrs at 37°C. Antimicrobial activity was measured by clear zones around the well [15-16].

3. IDENTIFICATION AND BIOCHEMICAL CHARACTERIZATION OF MARINE ISOLATES

3.1. Gram's staining

The pure marine isolates with antimicrobial activity were selected and performed Gram's staining. A loop of culture is taken and smear was prepared onto a clean glass slide. The smear is heat fixed and

initially crystal violet stain is added on the slide drop wise and allowed for a minute and washed with distilled water followed by mordant (Gram's Iodine) and decolorized with 95% ethyl alcohol slowly onto the glass slide until violet color disappears. At last counter stain is added allowed for 30secs and washed with distilled water. The culture slide is air dried and observed under microscope. Microorganisms were identified based on their color as Gram positive for purple or violet and Gram negative for pink.

3.2. Biochemical Characterization

KB001 Biochemical test kit is used to identify the Gram negative rods and KB002 biochemical test kit is for *Enterobacteriaceae*. About 50µl of inoculum is placed on each well of the KB001 and KB002 Kit and incubated at 37°C for 24 hours. After the incubation a series of reagents was added to respective wells and biochemical test results were interpreted based on the color change [17].

4. MOLECULAR IDENTIFICATION OF BACTERIAL STRAINS

4.1. Extraction of DNA

Hi Media spin column kit was used to extract chromosomal DNA from the sample for bacterial 16S rRNA gene 1500 base pairs was amplified using polymerase chain reaction in a thermal cycler and were purified using Exonuclease I - Shrimp Alkaline Phosphatase (Exo-SAP) [18].

4.2. DNA sequencing

For DNA sequencing BLAST algorithms was used to gather Evolutionary and Functional relationships to identify members of gene families. The BLASTN program was used to search and find the close type of strains [19]. Data alignment was carried out to Pair and calculate the sequence similarity values between the sequences to be identified and the query sequence. Each marine isolates were reported with top 10 hits observed in the data.

4.3. Phylogenetic tree

The Strain MB4 evolutionary history of was concluded by using the Tamura-Nei model and Maximum Likelihood method [20]. These Evolutionary analyses were conducted in MEGA11. The highest log likelihood (-5375.58) was shown in the tree, Next to the tree branch its percentage associated with the taxa clustered were noted by applying the Bio NJ algorithms and Neighbor-Join method initial tree search, Matrix of pair wise distances was estimated using the Tamura-Nei model, and then selecting the topology with superior log likelihood value, 10 nucleotide sequences were involved in this analysis in which over all 813 positions were found in the final data.

4.4. GENBANK submission

After sequence analysis the sequence data was submitted to GENBANK using BANKIT tool of NCBI and accession numbers for the marine isolates were obtained.

4.5. UV spectral analysis:

UV spectroscopy is the most common analytical study used for quantitative identification of high conjugated organic compounds, biological macromolecules, and some transition metal ions. The culture supernatant of MB4 was subjected to UV spectral analysis by using UV – 1800 [SHIMADZU] to study the optical density for absorbance measurement from 400nm -600nm [21].

5. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

5.1. Isolation of Marine Bacteria:

Eight different types of Marine bacterial strains were isolated by Spread plate technique on Zobell marine agar medium and Nutrient medium showed in the *Figure -1*, among them three were pigmented bacteria.

FIGURE-1. Screening of Pigmented Marine Bacteria on ZMA

5.2. Screening of Marine Isolates for its Antimicrobial activity

Eight marine bacteria were isolated from sea water sample. The assay showed all the eight strains inhibited at least one test organisms (Table-1). MB4 showed antimicrobial activity against all the test organisms. Antibiotic Gentamicin 30mcg is used as standard drug for bacterial pathogens whereas Fluconazole 25 mcg is used as drug against fungal pathogens.

TABLE-1 Screening of Marine Isolates for its Antimicrobial activity

Sample codes	Anti-Bacterial activity						Anti - Fungal activity			
	EC	SA	KP	ST	PM	AB	AN	AF	FF	AC
MB1	+	-	-	+	-	-	-	+	-	-
MB2	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	+	+	-
MB3	-	-	+	+	+	-	-	-	+	-
MB4	++	++	+	+	+	++	++	++	+	+
MB5	++	+	-	++	+	-	+	++	+	-
MB6	-	-	++	-	-	+	-	-	-	-
MB7	-	+	-	-	-	-	+	-	-	-
MB8	+	-	-	+	-	-	+	-	-	-

The Test microorganisms are: EC -*Escherichia coli*, SA-*Staphylococcus aureus*, KP-*Klebsiella pneumonia* ST- *Salmonella paratyphi b*, PM- *Proteus mirabilis*, AB-*Actinobacteria*. **FUNGI:** AN *Aspergillus niger* AF *Aspergillus flavus*, FF *Fusarium fujikuroi* AC *Aspergillus Clavatus*

-: No inhibition + inhibition zone was 0~5mm; ++: inhibition zone was 5~10mm, +++: inhibition zone was \geq 10mm

5.3. Colony morphology and biochemical characterization of Halophilic marine bacteria MB4

The morphological characterization of Marine bacteria MB4 on Zobell marine agar is shown in *Figure -2*

FIGURE-2. Colony morphology of Marine bacteria MB4 (*Kocuria flava*)

Marine isolate MB4 Colonies are small in size with smooth surface, slightly convex with entire edge, aerobic, non-motile, and yellow in color due to production of pigment.

5.5. Gram's staining

The Results of Grams staining of the marine strains under microscopic observation was showed in *figure -3* based on that observation, MB4 Marine strain was identified as micro cocci Gram's positive bacteria.

FIGURE -3. Gram's staining of MB4

5.6. Biochemical characterization

The Biochemical test result of MB4 was recorded based on the color change of the Biochemical test kit KB002 in *Figure-4*, which shows methyl red test as positive, catalase positive, oxidase test negative, citrate utilization test negative, lysine utilization was negative, Ornithine utilization was negative, urease negative, TDA reagent was used for phenylalanine deaminase test were no color change is observed, nitrate reduction is positive, H₂S production is not observed, only glucose showed positive result remaining lactose, arabinose, sorbitol showed negative result. Based on this report the marine bacteria MB4 is identified as *Kocuria sp.*

FIGURE-4. Biochemical Characterization of Marine Bacteria MB4

5.7. Molecular Identification of Bacteria

The *Figure-5* shows the PCR product gel image of Marine strains MB4, which was further analyzed for 16S r RNA ribosomal sequencing.

FIGURE-5. PCR product gel image

5.8. Phylogenetic tree

Good quality sequence data was used for comparison and Phylogenetic analysis [22]. Based on the molecular level of identification the marine isolate MB4 is identified as *Kocuria flava* shown in the Figure-6

FIGURE-6. Phylogenetic tree of MO1 (along with bootstrap values above 50%), the phylogeny of the strain MB4 showed close homology of 97% with the strain NR 044308 .1 *Kocuria flava* strain HO-9041

5.9. Genbank submission

Genomic nucleotide sequences were submitted to Gen bank using **BANKIT** tool and obtained accession numbers from Genbank for the Marine strains MB4 is MN227556

5.10. UV spectral analysis:

UV spectral analysis was carried out for the cultural supernatant of MB4. The samples were subjected to UV spectroscopy UV – 1800(SHIMADZU).The optical density of the MB4 sample was measured from 400 to 600nm shows highest peak at the wavelength of 435nm, shown in the *Figure-7*. The highest peak of 435nm in MB4 sample is similar to the peak of carotenoid which is yellow secondary metabolite present in the *Kocuria flava*.

Figure-7. UV Spectroscopy of MB4 showing highest peak of absorbance at 435 nm

6. DISCUSSION

Previously there were many works on marine therapeutic screening and ecological researches about the association of bacteria and fungi with sponges. Many investigations were carried out about the Antimicrobial activity of marine bacteria isolated from sea water and our results were consistent with those reports [23]. In our study around 10 isolates with pigments was isolated. Among these marine bacteria mainly we screened for the Antimicrobial compound producing bacteria. It is interesting to note that MB4 showed a board spectrum activity against human pathogens *Staphylococcus saprophyticus*, *Escherichia coli*, *Klebsiella pneumonia*, *Salmonella paratyphi-b*, *Proteus mirabilis*, *Actinobacteria*. Fungi such as *Aspergillus niger*, *Aspergillus flavus*, *Fusarium fujikuroi*, *Aspergillus clavatus*. The strain which showing enhanced potential activity was respectively carried out for further identification testes such as morphological, biochemical tests and 16S r RNA sequencing for molecular level identification of the marine isolate. The results of UV spectroscopy analysis of MB4 showed the highest peak related to carotenoid at 435nm [24]. Even though our present research facing few difficulty to scientific progress from past ten years for search of Novel Microorganism and Novel bioactive metabolites which leads to exploitation of new microbial strains for primary and secondary metabolites[25]. Based on the molecular level of identification the marine isolate MB4 is identified as *Kocuria flava*. The results of the study itself shows that marine isolates MB4 can be used as the source for identification of New Bio molecules which can be induced to produce new promising antibiotics.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

Authors are thankful to Department of Applied microbiology, DST- FIST and CURIE of SPMVV for providing research facilities to carry out the Research work.

REFERENCES

- [1] J.G Burgess, E.M Jordan, M. Breug, A. Mearns-Spragg, K.G. Boyd. "Microbial antagonism: a neglected avenue of natural products research", *J.Biotechnol*, (1999), 70:27-32.
- [2] B.K.Carte, "*Biomedical potential of marine natural products*", *Bioscience*, (1996), 46:271-286.
- [3] T. J. Abraham, "Antibacterial marine bacterium deters luminous vibriosis in shrimp larvae". *NAGA, World fish Centre Quarterly* (2004)27(3):28-30.
- [4] V. Janaki Devi, M. Yokesh Babu, and R. Uma rani. "Antagonistic activity of sea weed associated bacteria against human pathogens". *Int J curr Microbiol Appl Sci* (2013), 140-145.
- [5] A.R. Srividya, G.S. Saritha and B. Suresh, "Study of the soil isolates for antimicrobial activity". *Indian journal of pharmaceutical sciences* (2008) Nov; 70(6): 2-5.
- [6] G.V. Doern, M.A. Pfaller, and M .E. Erwin. "The prevalence of fluoroquinolone resistance among clinically significant respiratory tract isolates of streptococcus pneumonia in the United States and Canada-1997 results from the SENTRY Antimicrobial surveillance program". *Diagn Micro biolinfec Dis* (1998), 32:313-6.
- [7] N.Fatima, and S .Ishrat, "Frequency and risk factors of asymptomatic bacteriuria during pregnancy". *J Coll Physicians Surg Pak* (2006) 16: 273-275.
- [8] Adzzie-Shazleen Azman, Iekhsan Othman, Saraswati S velu, Kok-Gan Chan and Learn-Han Lee, "Mangrove rare actinobacteria: taxonomy,natural compound, and discovery of bioactivity". *Frontiers in Microbiology*, (2015) 6:856.
- [9] M.A. Fisch bach and C.T. Walsh. "Antibiotics for emerging pathogens". *Science* (2009) Aug 28; 325(5944):1089-93.
- [10] G.M. Cragg and D.J Newman, "Natural products: a continuing source of novel drug leads", *Biochemical and bio physica acta* (2013) June, 1830(6):3670-95.
- [11] T. Prem Anand, C.Chellaram,and S.Kumaran, "Screening for antibiotic producing marine bacteria against fish pathogens".*Int J Pharma Bio Sci* (2011);2(1):314-324.
- [12] C.M.Waters, B.L. Bassler, "Quorum sensing: cell-to-cell communication in bacteria", *Annu Rev Cell Dev Biol* (2005); 21:319-46.
- [13] J.Schnure, and J. Magnusson, "Antifungal lactic acid bacteria as bio preservatives" *Trends in food sciences and technology*, (2005).16(1-3), 70-78.
- [14] M.T Madian, J. M. Martinko, J. Parker and T. D. Brock, Text book of "Biology of Microorganism", Prentice-Hall, Inc ,NewJersey, USA(2000).
- [15] A. Isnansetyo and Y. Kamei, "Pseudalteromonasphenolica sp. nov., a novel marine bacterium that produces phenolic anti-methicillin-resistant Staphylococcus aureus substances", *International Journal of Systematic and Evolutionary Microbiology* (2003), 53(2):583–588.
- [16] O.K Radjasa and A.Sabdana, "Screening of Secondary metabolite-Producing bacteria associated with corals using 16Sr DNA-based approach" *J.Coast,Dev vol.7*(2003), :11-19.
- [17] N. Kannan, "Laboratory Manual in General Microbiology", Panima Publishers (2002).
- [18] J.E. Clarridge 3rd, "Impact of 16S r RNA gene sequence analysis for identification of bacteria on clinical microbiology and infectious diseases", *Clin Micro biol Rev*, (2004) October, 17 (4)840-62.
- [19] S. F. Altschul, W.Gish, W. Miller, E. Myers, and D.J Lipman, "Basic local alignment search tool". *J. Mol. Biol.*215, (1990), 403-410.
- [20] K. Tamura and M. Nei, "Estimation of the number of nucleotide substitutions in the control region of mitochondrial DNA in humans and chimpanzees". *Molecular Biology and Evolution* (1993). Vol .10:512-526.
- [21] L. Wind Szymanski, "Quantification of scattering corrections to the Beer-Lambert law for transmittance measurements in turbid media". *Meas Sci Technol.* (2002) 13: 951-270.
- [22] N. Saitou and M. Nei, "The neighbour-joining method: A new method for reconstructing phylogenetic tree",*molecular biology and evolution* (1987). 4:406-425.
- [23] T. Kohler, J.C. Pechere and P.Plesiat, "Bacteria; antibiotic efflux systems of medical importance," *Cell.Mol.Life Sci.*(1999)771-778.
- [24] J. Mercy, K. Aruna , "Optimization of pigment production by *Kocuria flava* isolated from garden soil", *Journal of Global Biosciences.* (2019)8(2): 5946-5965.
- [25] A. Kelecom Secondary metabolites from marine microorganisms .*Ann. Brazil Acad . Sci.*, (2002)74:151-170.